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Impact of Foliar Application of Micronutrients on Tomato Cv. 'Sahil' Under the Agro-Climatic Conditions of Dera Ismail Khan

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Abstract

The Research was conducted with the main objective to study the influence of foliar application of micronutrients on Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) cv. 'Sahil' at Agricultural Research Institute, Horticulture, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan during 2016-2017. The experiment consists of eight treatments involving T1 (RD NPK through chemical fertilizers N: P2O5 : K2 O5 kg ha⁻¹ (75 : 37.5 : 62.5)), T2 (T1+ Boric acid 0.571 g l⁻¹), T3 (T1+ Zinc sulphate 0.246 g l⁻¹), T4 (T1 + Copper sulphate 0.420 g l⁻¹), T5 (T1+Ferrous sulphate 0.515 g l⁻¹), T6 (T1 + Manganese sulphate 0.320 g l⁻¹) and T7 (T1 + mixture of all micronutrients) and T8 (T1 + Multiplex 4 ml l⁻¹) by mixing with simple water were imposed. The foliar application was made by using equipment knapsack sprayer (ASPEE) in the evening hours. The thrice times foliar spray were made at 10 days intervals starting from 40 days after transplanting seedling. The data clearly showed that the yield obtained with treatment T7 had significantly plant height (132.77 cm), number of branches plant⁻¹ (5.96), fresh weight of plants (25.70 t ha⁻¹), dry matter yield of plants (7669.04 kg ha⁻¹), maximum days to last picking (166.01), number of fruits plant⁻¹ (34.43), fruit length (5.47 cm), fruit diameter (4.57 cm), fruit volume (65.94 cm³), single fruit weight (49.00 g), fruit weight plant⁻¹ (1.69 kg), number of locules fruit⁻¹ (3.01), pericarp thickness (6.27 mm), fruit yield plot-1 (70.86 kg), fruit yield ha⁻¹ (46.87 t.) and marketable fruit yield ha⁻¹ (45.68 t). This treatment had maximum BCR 2.71: 1 out all other treatments than control.

Key words: Micronutrient, Tomato, yield, yield components, BCR

Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Miller) is one of the most important vegetable crop, belongs to family solanaceae, originated in Pakistan. It is a leading vegetable crop grown across the length and breadth of country due to its wide adaptability of various agro-climatic conditions. It is equally liked by both poor and rich and is quite high in nutritive value. It is on the top of the list of processing vegetable and is a good source of vitamin A and C. Hence, it is called as "Poor Man's Orange." It also plays an important role in processing industries and hence in Pakistan economics. It is generally consumed as salad and mixed in vegetable curries to add taste, colour and flavour. It possesses many health benefits which include urinary tract infection, skin problems, diabetes, hypertension and various cancers. Micronutrients are not only essential for better growth, yield and quality, but also important like other major nutrients in spite of their requirement in micro quantity. It also helps in uptake of major nutrients and also vital to the growth of plants acting as catalyst in promoting various organic reaction from cell development to respiration, photosynthesis, chlorophyll formation, enzyme activity, hormones synthesis and nitrogen fixation. The production and productivity of crop is being adversely affected in areas due to deficiencies of micronutrients. The micronutrient deficiencies have appeared in recent years due to intensive cropping, loss of top soil by erosion, loss due to leaching, limiting soils and decreased availability and use of organic matter. One way of overcoming micronutrient deficiency in crop instantly is foliar

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application of micronutrients. Looking to the importance of the crop, future scope and heavy demand of tomato fruits for the domestic as well as export business and for processing industry, a field trial entitled “influence of foliar application of micronutrients on Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) cv. 'Sahil' was conducted at Agricultural Research Institute, Horticulture, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan.

Materials and methods

The investigation was carried out at Agricultural Research Institute, Horticulture, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan during 2017-2018. In all eight treatments *viz.*, eight treatments involving T1 (RD NPK through chemical fertilizers N: P₂O₅ : K₂O 5 kg ha⁻¹ (75 : 37.5 : 62.5)), T2 (T1+ Boric acid 0.571 g l⁻¹), T3 (T1+ Zinc sulphate 0.246 g l⁻¹), T4 (T1 + Copper sulphate 0.420 g l⁻¹), T5 (T1+Ferrous sulphate 0.515 g l⁻¹), T6 (T1 + Manganese sulphate 0.320 g l⁻¹) and T7 (T1 + mixture of all micronutrients) and T8 (T1 + Multiplex 4 ml l⁻¹) were evaluated in a Randomized Block Design with five replications. The tomato cv. Vegnish seedlings nursery was raised at 15 cm x 7 cm distance in a plot size 3 x 1 m and transplanted in plot size 4.2 m X 3.6 m. All agronomical practices were taken normally.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses of the data were performed as per ANOVA techniques (Steel et al., 1980) and significant results were subjected to LSD test for mean comparison using MSTATC software (MSTATC, 1991).

Results and discussion

The data clearly indicated that the growth and yield of crop obtained with treatment T7 (T1 + mixture of all micronutrients thrice times foliar spray at 10 days interval starting from 40 days after transplanting seedling) had showed significantly higher plant height (132.77 cm), number of branches plant⁻¹ (5.96), fresh weight of plants ha⁻¹ (25.70 t.), dry matter yield of plant ha⁻¹ (7669.04 kg), maximum harvesting period of days to last picking (166.01), number of fruits plant⁻¹ (34.43), fruit length (5.47 cm), fruit diameter (4.57 cm), fruit volume (65.94 cm³), single fruit weight (49 g), fruit weight plant⁻¹ (1.69 kg), number of locules fruit⁻¹ (3.01), pericarp thickness (6.27 mm), fruit yield plot-1 (70.86 kg), fruit yield ha⁻¹ (46.87 t) and marketable fruit yield ha⁻¹ (45.68 t), respectively in tables 1 and 2. It had highest high net maximum realization of Rs 1, 36,752.00 / ha. These findings are in conformity with the results of Bhatt et al. (2004) and Patil et al. (2008), who obtained maximum benefit: cost ratio with foliar application of mixture of all micronutrients. The T8 (T1 + (Zn 3 %, Mn 1%, B 0.5% and Fe 2%) multiplex 4 ml/lit of simple water) foliar thrice times foliar spray at 10 days intervals starting from 40 days after transplanting seedling had positive effects next to T7 consisting of the combination of inorganic fertilizer plus mixture of all micronutrients produced for particularly higher plant height (129.06 cm), number of branches plant⁻¹ (5.92), fresh weight of plant ha⁻¹ (25.18 t), dry matter yield of plant ha⁻¹ (7604.91 kg), maximum harvesting period of days to last picking (165.39), number of fruits plant⁻¹ (33.84), fruit size (5.423 cm), fruit diameter (4.40 cm), fruit volume (64.00 cm³), single fruit weight (43.40 g), fruit weight plant⁻¹ (1.47 kg), number of locules fruit⁻¹ (2.65), pericarp thickness (6.09 mm), fruit yield plot-1 (61.77 kg), fruit yield ha⁻¹ (40.85 t) and marketable fruit yield ha⁻¹ (40.85 t) than the remaining treatments. This might due to the enhancement in photosynthesis and other metabolic activity which led to an increase in various plant metabolites responsible for cell division and elongation results improvement in growth characters (Hatwar *et al.*, 2003). Increased yield due to micronutrients application may be attributed to enhanced photosynthetic activity, resulting into the increased production and accumulation of carbohydrate and favourable effect on vegetative growth and retention of flower and fruits which might have increased number of fruits per plant besides improvement in the fruit size. The increase in dry matter production of fruits may be attributed to greater accumulation of photosynthates by vegetative parts and its subsequent translocation to the sink. Also role of boron which enhance the movement of sugar borate complex from the leaves to the fruit and ultimately increased the fruit yield according to result given by Pandita et al. (1976); Singh et al. (2003).

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Table 1. Effect of foliar application of micronutrients on Tomato cv. Sahil

Treatment	Days to 50 % flowering	Plant height (cm)	Number of branches plant ⁻¹	Fresh weight of plant (t. ha ⁻¹)	Dry matter content of plant (kg ha ⁻¹)	Days to first picking	Days to last picking	Number of fruits plant ⁻¹
T1	32.1	80.21	3.41	19.13	5981.32	90.61	142.38	22.43
T2	34.80	98.71	4.71	23.21	6854.41	82.41	157.81	31.19
T3	34.10	111.21	4.27	23.32	7441.41	80.71	162.53	31.18
T4	34.9	83.31	3.51	20.32	6597.11	86.61	146.55	25.62
T5	33.61	84.41	3.53	21.81	6791.81	83.54	152.85	26.19
T6	31.71	88.56	3.95	22.50	6818.01	82.80	155.41	29.30
T7	35.41	131.11	5.91	25.31	7668.01	75.21	167.01	34.41
T8	35.45	129.45	5.89	25.19	7614.92	73.88	166.31	33.80
SEm ±	0.53	2.98	0.28	1.31	257.14	1.84	3.78	1.48
C. D _{0.05}	1.59**	8.68**	0.76**	3.77**	743.02**	5.30**	10.93**	4.26**

Table 2. Effect of foliar application of micronutrients on Tomato cv. Sahil

Treatment	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit diameter (cm)	Fruit volume (cm ³)	Fruit weight (g)	Fruit yield (kg plant ⁻¹)	No. of locules fruit ⁻¹	Fruit yield (kg plot ⁻¹)	Total fruit yield (ton ha ⁻¹)	Marketable fruit yield (ton ha ⁻¹)	BCR
T1	9.08	3.44	49.88	33.01	0.75	2.28	31.04	20.51	18.77	3.95
T2	5.01	4.09	61.72	41.21	1.29	2.72	53.91	35.61	32.92	4.54
T3	5.23	4.21	62.71	44.51	1.40	2.66	58.57	38.71	37.09	4.25
T4	4.34	3.80	55.29	36.01	0.91	2.32	38.61	25.57	23.18	4.78
T5	4.52	3.81	56.21	38.61	1.02	2.31	42.62	28.19	26.18	4.69
T6	4.81	4.01	58.22	33.41	0.99	2.33	41.03	27.15	24.17	4.48
T7	5.48	4.58	65.35	49.01	1.67	3.02	70.88	46.89	45.67	4.86
T8	5.24	4.41	64.01	43.41	1.48	2.66	61.78	40.83	39.56	4.77
SEm ±	0.26	0.17	3.09	1.24	0.09	0.12	3.27	2.16	2.11	0.62
C. D _{0.05}	0.75**	0.47**	8.90**	3.57**	0.24**	0.32**	9.51**	6.29**	6.08**	NS

Conclusion

From the forgoing discussion, it can be concluded that foliar spray of T7 (T1 + mixture of all micronutrients) effective which much more effective than control. Also observed much enhance maximum plant height, number of branches plant⁻¹, fresh weight of plant ha⁻¹, dry matter yield of plant⁻¹, minimum days to first picking and maximum days to last picking, number of fruits plant⁻¹, fruit length (cm), fruit diameter (cm), single fruit weight (g), fruit weight plant⁻¹, number of locules fruit⁻¹, pericarp thickness (mm), fruit yield plot⁻¹, fruit yield ha⁻¹ and marketable fruit yield ha⁻¹ and BCR ratio out all other treatments than control. The growth and yield attributes of tomato cv. Sahil showed positive results for spraying of T7 (T1 + mixture of all micronutrient thrice times foliar spray at 10 days interval starting from 40 days after transplanting seedling) treatment then followed by T8 (T1 + multiplex 4 ml/lit of simple water) treatment.

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Author's Contribution

Imran Ullah: As a principal author conducted the research, Shitab Khan: Supervised the study and provided technical input at every step, Niamat Ullah Khan: wrote the manuscript and prepared the draft, Aftab Ahmad khan: Analyzed the lab work.

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